

Spectrum Occupancy Detection Supported by Federated Learning

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Outline

- Introduction
- Federated Learning
- Data Collection
- Simulation Setup
- Simulation Results
- Conclusions

Introduction

- Radio services demand
- Dynamic spectrum access
- Spectrum occupancy detection
- Machine learning
- Distributed decision making
- Security of data

Federated Learning

- Single sensor creates own model (own data)
- Single sensor makes own decisions
- In meantime each sensor sends own model coefficients to central node (or neighbours)
 - not decisions (cooperated sensing)
 - not users data (training of global model)
- Common model created based on received coefficients, send back to each sensor
- Each sensor uses result of merging of own model and common model

Data Collection

- Parameters

- Center frequency: 2100 MHz
- LO offset: 10 MHz
- Bandwidth: 40 MHz
- Effective bandwidth: 26 MHz
- Channel bandwidth: 1 MHz
- Transmitter modulation: GMSK

- Measurements repeated for many channels, however in this work only one was analyzed

Data Analysis

- For each channel, calculation of:
 - Average received power
 - Kurtosis of autocorrelation function
 - Skewness of autocorrelation function

Reference Model

- Probability of false alarm: 1%

Simulation Setup

- Input data divided to 5 virtual sensors

Simulation Setup

- Reference scenario: each model trains and decides separately
- Iterative approach

Validation metric:
Average accuracy
score among
all sensors

Simulation Setup

- Federated learning scenario: each model trains separately, then exchange model coefficients, (common model creation)

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Simulation Results

- Logistic Regression
- Each model has
 - 3 weights
 - 1 interception
- In common model median value is selected

Simulation Results

- Neural Network

- In common model median value is selected

Conclusions

- There is a potential for using federated learning in spectrum occupancy detection systems
- In some scenarios, they provide increased reliability of detection and, more importantly, ensure:
 - greater efficiency of decisions made compared to classic algorithms (energy detection)
 - comparable efficiency compared to algorithms which uses machine learning